

Population Genetic Structure of Massachusetts Spotted Turtles using Microsatellite Markers

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Abstract

We examined allelic diversity, genetic variability and population structure of three populations of spotted turtles in Massachusetts using six highly polymorphic microsatellite markers. Two of the populations were from the mainland (Canton and Halifax) and one was from Nantucket (Sanford Farm). Pairwise F_{st} and population assignment tests showed that overall, spotted turtles from all three locations belong to the same population. The two mainland populations are highly genetically similar and the Sanford Farm population is somewhat less genetically similar to the mainland groups. Assessment of allelic patterns indicates that the Sanford Farm population has the least allelic diversity, as it showed the fewest number of private alleles and the fewest number of different alleles at each locus

We also examined the relationship between two known spotted turtle populations on Nantucket. The two populations, at Sanford Farm and Medouie Creek, are virtually indistinguishable at two of the three loci that were tested.

Introduction

The spotted turtle (*Clemmys guttata*) is a small, semi aquatic turtle that is widely distributed from New England to Florida. Additionally, there are isolated colonies in Southern Quebec, Southern Ontario, Central Illinois, Central Georgia, Indiana and Ohio (Turtle Conservation Project, 2007). The spotted turtle has complex habitat requirements. In order to complete their life cycle, individuals require both aquatic and terrestrial habitats. They often occupy several different types of shallow, vegetation-rich wetlands, including marshy meadows, bogs, swamps, ponds, ditches, or small bodies of still water. The spotted turtle is a very mobile species and tends to rotate between wetlands, which require overland movements (Natural Heritage and Endangered Species Program, 2007).

Populations of the spotted turtle have greatly declined over the years, mainly due to various anthropogenic effects, leading them to be listed as an Endangered species at the federal

level in Canada and at the state level in the United States in Vermont, Indiana, and Illinois . In West Virginia they are listed as critically imperiled, and in Maine, Michigan, South Carolina, Ohio, and New York they are listed as Threatened (Estay, 2012).

In Massachusetts, spotted turtles were once on the Endangered Species list, however they were removed from this listing in 2006 (Eldred, 2006). Spotted turtles on the mainland are severely suffering the effects of habitat fragmentation; those on Nantucket face habitat fragmentation *and* genetic drift. A comparison among island and mainland populations could possibly help to determine appropriate conservation and management methods for populations that have become fragmented due to development or isolated due to their island location.

Molecular markers such as microsatellites, also known as STRS (short tandem repeats) are useful in assessing the genetic diversity and structure of a population. Microsatellites can either evolve by slippage of the polymerase during replication, or less frequently, by unequal cross over or gene conversion. The polymorphic allele sizes of the microsatellites at each locus can be used as a basis for genotyping individuals. The alleles can be amplified by polymerase chain reaction (PCR) for genotyping and the sizes of the alleles can be assessed using a DNA sequencer.

The purpose of the study was to expand on a preliminary study using microsatellite DNA markers to assess population genetic diversity and relatedness among Massachusetts spotted turtle populations. The preliminary study, performed by Mae Ciampa (Wheaton '11) involved the comparison of a mainland population (Halifax) and a Nantucket island population (Medouie Creek). Our study adds to the sample size of the Halifax population and also adds two new populations—a mainland population (Canton) and island population (Sanford Farm). We also looked at the relatedness of the two Nantucket populations of spotted turtles at Medouie Creek and Sanford Farm with respect to each other.

Methods

Sample collection and isolation

The total spotted turtle sample size was 100 individuals: 36 from Medouie Creek, 24 from Halifax, 20 from Canton, and 20 from Sanford Farm. The spotted turtle blood samples were preserved on Whatman FTA cards. The DNA was isolated following the QIAmp DNA mini kit protocol. The DNA samples were then stored at -20 C until amplification by PCR.

Confirmation of DNA Extraction

We confirmed successful extraction and isolation of the spotted turtle DNA by electrophoresing the samples on 0.8% agarose gels using Tris/Acetate/EDTA buffer and staining with Ethidium Bromide. After electrophoresis, the gels were photographed and visualized with the computer program KODAK MI under UV light.

PCR (Polymerase Chain Reaction) amplification

We amplified spotted turtle DNA using PCR, and then electrophoresed the PCR products on 1.5% agarose gels to confirm amplification. The seven microsatellite loci (GmuD16, GmuD40, GmuD55, GmuD70, GmuD87, GmuD93, GmuD121 (King and Julian, 2004) were amplified using fluorescently labeled (WellREad dyes; SigmaGenoSys) for forward primer sequences. Table 1 provides the identity of the seven primers used, and the florescent color in Beckmen-Coulter CEQ800 fragment analysis.

15 ul reactions were prepared using 1.5 μ L of spotted turtle DNA as template. The PCR reagents and concentrations (Table 2) were prepared as a master mix, of which 13.5 μ l was added to each tube.

The reaction tubes were then transferred into the racks of the MJ Research PTC-200 DNA Engine Thermal Cycler. DNA was amplified under the following conditions: 94 degrees for 2 minutes followed by a cycle that was repeated 35 times: 94 for 45 seconds, 58 degrees for 45 seconds, 72 degrees for 90 seconds.

Sample preparation for fragment analysis on the CEQ-8000 sequencer

The CEQ-8000 sequencer is a genetic analysis system provides accurate and high precision sizing of amplified fragments for automated allele identification. The samples were loaded onto a 96 well plate and separated on the Beckman CEQ-800 sequencer. Each well of the plate consisted of 1 ul of sample, and a buffer/size standard mixture (38.5 ul Beckman SLS buffer, and 0.5 ul of 400 bp DNA size standard). After the sample and buffer/ladder mixture were loaded, one drop of mineral oil was added. The plates were then centrifuged. A second 96 well mirror plate was prepared with 10 drops separation buffer in each well corresponding to the sample plate.

After the fragments were separated, they were analyzed with the Fragment Analysis program (Beckman-Coulter) using the default options. Each primer generated either one peak in

individuals homozygous at the amplified locus or two peaks in heterozygous individuals. The allele fragment sizes were standardized between runs by a process called “binning.”

Statistical Analyses

The allele sizes at each locus were recorded as genotypes and entered into Microsoft Excel 2007. First, the data were analyzed using the software program, Microchecker, to identify genotyping errors, null alleles, and to assess typographic errors. After the data was edited, a spreadsheet for GeneAlex, version 6.41b was created. GeneAlex determined allelic variation, allele frequencies, mean allelic patterns across populations, Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium, molecular variance, F-statistics across loci, and pairwise F-statistics.

Results

The GenomeLab Fragment program was used to analyze the sizes of the microsatellite loci. Before the data was entered into the analysis programs, the software program, Micro-Checker, was used to assess the quality of the data by identifying null alleles, large allele dropouts, typographic errors, and the scoring error due to stuttering.

Micro-checker also detected the presence of null alleles. The null alleles that most adversely impacted the data were at locus GmuD93 and GmuD87. The null allele at GmuD93 was detected in each population. Unfortunately, it altered the mean heterozygosity frequencies, the Hardy-Weinberg Test, and the Fis analysis. The null allele at GmuD87 was only detected in the Halifax population; however, it significantly distorted the data such that the data from the locus was removed from the entire analysis.

Allele sizes and quantity at each loci

At each of six loci, the samples were genotyped and the allele sizes were determined. Table 3 lists the number of alleles found at each locus and their size range.

The largest number of different alleles (22) was detected at locus GmuD93 while the largest size range of alleles was observed at the GmuD55 locus (144-344 base pairs).

Mean allelic patterns across populations

The highest allelic variation and diversity was observed in the Halifax population, while the least was observed in the Sanford Farm population. Figure 1 displays the results graphically while Table 4 summarizes the mean results for the allelic patterns.

Although the numbers show a trend, there was no significant difference in the mean number of effective alleles (N_e), Shannon Information index (I), and heterozygosity among the populations. The effective number of alleles (N_e) is a measurement of the alleles that would be expected at a locus in each population. It takes into account allele frequencies and is less sensitive to rare alleles. Diversity relates more to effective number of alleles rather than heterozygosity. Shannon index, also known as Shannon entropy, quantifies the uncertainty in predicting the identity of an individual that is taken at random from the data set. It is based on the weighted geometric mean of the proportional abundances of the different types of alleles. A high index for a population signifies that there is more genetic diversity. The most significant finding in this series of tests is the calculation of the number of private alleles, i.e. the number of alleles that are unique to a population. The number of private alleles in the Sanford Farm population was 3 to 6-fold lower than in turtles from the mainland.

Heterozygosities Null alleles and Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium

GenAlex was used to calculate observed and expected heterozygosity frequencies at each locus and the probability that the populations were under Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium. As mentioned, Micro-Checker was used to estimate null allele frequencies and whether the frequency was significant. The significance of null allele frequencies is important because if an allele is not amplifying, the mean heterozygosity and Hardy-Weinberg calculations are distorted.

Hardy-Weinberg Equilibrium (HWE) exists when gene and genotype frequencies are constant from one generation to the next. In the HWE test, the observed genotype frequencies are compared to theoretical frequencies that assume the following conditions: no random mating, no mutation, no drift, and no migration. Table 5 shows the heterozygosity frequencies for observed versus expected, the probability of deviation from Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium, and the null allele probability estimate. Many loci did not show significant deviation from Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium. Those deviations from HWE, which were noted, could be the result of small sample sizes. The GmuD16 locus consistently passed the HWT in all populations. Halifax spotted turtles had the greatest number of loci that deviated from the HWE.

There were high heterozygosity values for most microsatellites in the three populations. Thus, by this measure, human activities and isolation on an island do not seem to have an influence on the genetic diversity of these populations.

The null allele at GmuD93 caused observed homozygote excess for each population. This explains why there was the most significant deviation from HWE ($p < 0.05$) for the Halifax and Canton populations. The HWT for the Sanford Farm population showed that although there was a null allele present and homozygote excess at the locus GmuD93, this locus did not significantly deviate from HWE.

Population substructures: AMOVA and Fst

Analysis of Molecular Variance (AMOVA) was determined with GenAlex. AMOVA is a statistical method that describes the partitioning of genetic variance between and within populations. When there is no substructuring, 100% of the genetic variance is within populations and 0% is among populations. The result of AMOVA is illustrated in Figure 2. The AMOVA of the three populations showed that 96% of total variation was within populations and 4% was among populations. These results show that there is a very low degree of population substructuring. It is not surprising that there is a low degree of substructuring between Canton and Halifax because those are the mainland populations; however, due to geographic isolation, it was expected that the inclusion of Sanford Farms would indicate additional substructuring when all three populations are included.

F-statistics for population pairs.

Overall, the Fst pairwise population pair analysis showed that all of the populations were fairly similar because the values are very close to zero (Table 6). However, the mainland populations were much more similar to one another than to Sanford Farm.

Population assignment

Frequency based assignment tests were determined between the Halifax population (Pop 1) and the Canton population (Pop 2) using the leave-one-out method in the program GenAlex 6.2. The genotype of each sample was compared to the allele frequencies observed in either the Halifax and Canton populations with log-likelihoods. With log-likelihoods as negative values, the highest (least negative) value indicates the most likely population. Fig. 3. and Table 7 summarizes the population assignment test. Figure 3. displays a large overlap of the genetic profile of each individual in the three different populations. This suggests a similarity of the microsatellite alleles and points to the presence of a single population of spotted turtles in Southeast MA and Nantucket. The graph indicates that many of the individuals for the Canton

and Halifax population are genetically indistinguishable from one another, and that the Sanford Farm population is similar to the mainland populations.

However, when a population assignment test is performed with all three populations, all but four of the individuals from Sanford Farm were assigned to their own population (Table 7). Of the four individuals, two were assigned to Halifax and the other two to Canton.

Comparison of two Nantucket populations of spotted turtles.

In the above genetic comparison of spotted turtles on mainland sites, compared to a Nantucket population, only the turtles at Sanford Farms were used in the analysis. We also had access to DNA from spotted turtles at Medouie Creek on Nantucket. We compared a random sample of 16 spotted turtles from Sanford Farm to a random sample of 16 spotted turtles from Medouie Creek at three microsatellite loci (Table 8). Using pairwise F_{st} values as an index, the two Nantucket populations are indistinguishable (close to 0) at two of the three loci and very similar to one another at the third locus.

Discussion

Due to the geographical separation of Nantucket from mainland Massachusetts, we predicted genetic divergence and population structuring among the spotted turtle clusters that we examined. In addition, habitat fragmentation, small population sizes, low dispersal capacity, and relatively low reproductive rate were also expected to contribute to population structuring in Massachusetts spotted turtles. We also expected to observe less genetic diversity in spotted turtles from Nantucket. Our findings do not support these predictions.

By various measures, we found that two geographically distinct spotted turtle clusters in southeastern Massachusetts (Halifax and Canton) are very similar to one another and also very similar to spotted turtles on Nantucket. Our genetic markers, microsatellites, are not believed to have adaptive value and thus mutate at higher rates than other genes. We therefore expected to see population differentiation. Instead, we found that Sanford Farms (Nantucket), Halifax and Canton spotted turtles appear to belong to a single population. There is a hint of substructuring, as suggested by pairwise F_{st} values, a population assignment test and the low number of private alleles in the Sanford Farm cluster. Because the populations are so similar, there may have been considerable historic gene flow, which occurred before the formation of Nantucket Island 5000-6000 years ago due to rising sea levels. We also found that two Nantucket clusters, Sanford

Farms and Medouie Creek, may be virtually indistinguishable. In addition, the overall level of genetic diversity in the Nantucket populations was comparable to mainland turtles

Our findings are preliminary and population sample sizes were low, but trends are still apparent. Though the results are unexpected, they are not unusual. Relatively low levels of genetic differentiation have been observed among different populations of several freshwater and brackish turtle species, even though these species occupy a wide range and are isolated by distances that would seemingly preclude gene flow (bog turtles: Rosenbaum et al., 2007; wood turtles: Tessler et al., 2005; diamondback terrapins: McCafferty et al., 2013).

It would be of interest to expand the study to other spotted turtle clusters throughout the range of the species to determine if the population structure we discovered in southeast Massachusetts is unique. It would also be of interest to examine these populations using genetic markers with adaptive value.

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Tables and Figures

primer name	dye	dye color
GmuD16	D2	black
GmuD40	D2	black
GmuD55	D3	green
GmuD70	D3	green
GmuD87	D4	blue
GmuD93	D2	black
GmuD121	D4	blue

Table 1. Primers used for PCR: primer's name, color, and the dye in Beckmen-Coulter CEQ800 fragment analysis.

Component	Concentration per Reaction
Taq polymerase	1 unit
5X GoTaq Flexi Buffer (Green)	1X
MgCl ₂	2 mM
dNTP	0.25 mM
Forward Primer (fluorescent)	0.5 μ M
Reverse Primer	0.5 μ M

Table 2: PCR reagents, all from Promega. Reagents were diluted in nuclease-free water. The formula for preparation of the Taq polymerase was one part Taq polymerase (5 units per μ L), one part 5X Gotaq buffer, and three parts nuclease free water.

	Total alleles	Size Range (Base pairs)
GmuD16	10	140-144
GmuD40	18	106-190
GmuD55	19	144-344
GmuD70	15	104-216
GmuD93	22	224-392
GmuD121	12	100-260

Table 3: The number of different alleles observed at each locus and the sizes across all populations.

	Halifax	Canton	Sanford Farm
Na	12.67	9.83	7.50
Na Freq. \geq 5%	5.67	7.17	5.50
Ne	7.28	5.89	4.61
I	2.18	1.95	1.63
No. Private Alleles	4.50	2.17	0.67
He	0.85	0.82	0.74

Table 4. Mean Allelic Patterns Across Populations: Na = No. of Different Alleles; Na (Freq \geq 5%) = No. of Different Alleles with a Frequency \geq 5%; Ne = No. of Effective Alleles = $1 / (\sum \pi^2)$; I = Shannon's Information Index = $-1 * \sum (\pi * \ln (\pi))$; No. Private Alleles = No. of Alleles Unique to a Single Population; He = Expected Heterozygosity = $1 - \sum \pi^2$

	Locus	Ho	He	Null Allele Estimates	Null Present	Prob	Signif
Halifax	GmuD16	0.71	0.87	0.07	no	0.435	ns
	GmuD40	0.91	0.91	-0.03	no	0.352	ns
	GmuD55	0.86	0.83	-0.04	no	0.027	*
	GmuD70	0.70	0.81	0.04	no	0.006	**
	GmuD93	0.52	0.89	0.21	yes	0.000	***
	GmuD121	0.88	0.81	-0.03	no	0.004	**
Canton	GmuD16	0.90	0.86	-0.03	no	0.058	ns
	GmuD40	0.70	0.86	0.10	yes	0.001	**
	GmuD55	0.74	0.79	0.06	no	0.156	ns
	GmuD70	0.80	0.84	0.01	no	0.331	ns
	GmuD93	0.50	0.86	0.20	yes	0.000	***
	GmuD121	0.94	0.70	-0.20	no	0.177	ns
Sanford Farm	GmuD16	0.70	0.75	-0.02	no	0.965	ns
	GmuD40	0.60	0.86	0.15	yes	0.008	**
	GmuD55	0.74	0.76	0.06	no	0.739	ns
	GmuD70	0.74	0.75	-0.03	no	0.000	***
	GmuD93	0.50	0.85	0.17	yes	0.072	ns
	GmuD121	0.68	0.50	-0.40	no	0.526	ns

Table 5 Test for deviation from Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium by loci. Key: ns=not significant, * P<0.05, ** P<0.01, * P<0.001**

	Halifax	Canton	Sanford Farm
Halifax	0.000		
Canton	0.018	0.000	
Sanford Farm	0.030	0.031	0.000

Table 6. Multilocus estimates for pairwise Fst values. The Halifax and Canton populations are the most genetically similar. Overall, the populations are fairly genetically similar, as the pairwise Fst values are close to 0.

Population	Self Population	Other Population
Halifax	10	14
Canton	8	12
Sanford Farm	16	4

Table 7. Summary of population assignment outcomes to “self” or “other” population.

Locus	Fst
D16	0.0014
D40	0.0947
D70	0.0041
All loci	0.0381

Table 8: Pairwise Fst: Sanford Farm compared to Medouie Creek

Figure 1: Microsatellite diversity patterns across populations. Whiskers represent standard errors. Na = No. of Different Alleles; Na (Freq >= 5%) = No. of Different Alleles with a Frequency >= 5%; Ne = No. of Effective Alleles = $1 / (\sum \pi^2)$; I = Shannon's Information Index = $-1 * \sum (\pi * \ln(\pi))$; No. Private Alleles = No. of Alleles Unique to a Single Population; He = Expected Heterozygosity = $1 - \sum \pi^2$

Figure 2: Analysis of Molecular (AMOVA) results from GeneAlex version 6.2. This statistical method shows that there is a very low degree of population substructuring.

Figure 3: Population Assignment Graph for All Populations. Pop 1,2, and 3 refer to Halifax, Canton, and Sanford Farm respectively.